

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

THE INCIDENCE OF ORAL CANDIDIASIS IN DIABETES¹ Dr. Ahmad Farooq, ² Dr. Khadija, ³ Dr. Ayesha Younas¹ Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi**Abstract:**

Background: this study was done in order to find of the frequency of oral fungal infection associated with diabetes type 2 and its correlation with the age, gender, glycemc control, timespan of illness and kind of therapy.

METHODS: This study was a cross sectional one, carried out at the medical unit 1, Benazir Bhutto hospital, Rawalpindi over the periods of 3months. This study included 305 diabetic patients admitted in the ward. Detail history of these patients was taken which included the age, family history, duration of illness, type of therapy and history of other comorbid. Oral examination of these patients was carried out to rule out candidiasis and grams staining were done from buccal mucosa scrapings to analyze fungal hyphae.

RESULTS: Out of 305 patients examined, 71 patients had oral candidiasis. 58.64% patients with and 57.50% patients without oral fungal infection were male (p value >0.05). Mean age of patients with and without oral candidiasis was 58.4 +5.76 and 53.76+5.62 respectively. 25.56% Diabetic patients taking hypoglycemic drugs had incidence of oral candidiasis, whereas the people who used insulin for glycemc control account for 23.34%. Risk of oral fungal infection was noted high with the duration of diabetes, 58% patients had oral candidiasis that had diabetes for last 10-15 years.

CONCLUSION: The incidence of oral fungal infection especially candidiasis increased with the duration of diabetes along with poor glycemc control and with the higher age group of the patients.

Keywords: Candidiasis, diabetes mellitus, oral hypoglycemic, insulin.

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Please cite this article in press Ahmad Farooq et al., *The Incidence Of Oral Candidiasis In Diabetes.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disease characterized by the increase blood sugar level. There are currently 2 main etiologies of diabetes i.e. the hypo secretion of insulinⁱ from pancreas and the reduced sensitivity of body cell toward insulinⁱⁱ. Diabetes has three main subtypes.

Type 1 DM (juvenile diabetes): this type mostly occurred in young people below the age of 30 years. This is due to hypo secretion of insulin from the Beta cell of pancreas.ⁱⁱⁱ

Type 2 DM (adult onset diabetes): this type occurred in obese patient above the age of 30 years. This is due to the decrease sensitivity of body cells toward the insulin.^{iv}

Gestational diabetes: Occurred in the pregnant women without the prior history of diabetes.

Studies conducted in this 2015 showed that 415^v million people had diabetes worldwide with type 2 diabetes covering the 90% of people^{vi}. Comparison of the recent studies depict that the incidence of diabetes keep on increasing rapidly. Diabetes increases risk of death by 2 folds. From the period 2012 to 2015, approximately 1.5 to 5.0 million^{vii} deaths every year occurred due to the diabetes.

Diabetes increased the risk of complication including both micro and Macro vascular complications. Macro vascular complications involve diabetic neuropathy, diabetic nephropathy, heart diseases, stroke and peripheral arterial disease. In micro vascular complications patient cutaneous manifestation are much important and in above group infection especially fungal infection are more frequent. Oral candidiasis is the more frequent fungal infection occurred in the diabetic patients^{viii}, present with the wipe able white plaques inside the oral cavity i.e. tongue buccal mucosa, palate, gingivae and the floor of mouth.

Different studies conducted nationally and internationally to find out the different factors for oral fungal infection in the diabetic patients. The major predisposing factors are oral hygiene, glycemic control, smoking,^x duration of diabetes, type of therapy and xerostomia. The studies showed the

incidence of oral candidiasis is much higher in diabetic patients as compare to the normal population. The average frequency of oral candidiasis among diabetic patients in Pakistan is 22.2%

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The cross sectional a study was done at the medical unit 1, Benazir Bhutto hospital, Rawalpindi from the period of June 2016 to September 2016. Total 305 of diabetics patients were included in this study with the age 45-65 years old, both male and female and diagnosed diabetic at least 5 years back. Patients recruited in this study were under the treatment in the form of either oral hypoglycemic drug or insulin or both. Patients with chronic liver disease, hematological malignancies, chronic kidney disease and patients taking steroids, immunosuppressive drugs were excluded from study. In this diabetic patient oral examination had been done under the adequate light by noting the whitish plaque covering the oral cavity and the buccal scrapings were taken with the edge of slide under the proper protocol of sterilization. These scrapings were shifting to other slides and slides were taken to the laboratory of hospital for the detection and confirmation of fungal hyphae after the gram staining.

The proper profomas were designed to collect the data according to the age, gender, timespan of diabetes, kind of treatment and presence or absence of fungal infection. In this way people were divided into two groups on the presence or absence of oral fungal infection.

RESULTS:

Total 305 patients were recruited in the study, out of which 190 were male and 115 were female. Mean age of the patients was 56.12±5.64. On examination 77 patients were found to have oral candidiasis and included in the group 1. The patients in this study have different duration of illness i.e. 224 patients have diabetes for last 5-10 years, 56 patients have diabetes for last 10-15 years and 25 for last 15-20 years.

Table 1: Comparison between candidiasis and patient without candidiasis.

	Group- I (With oral candidiasis)	Group- II (Without oral candidiasis)	p- value
Mean age (years)	58.4+5.76	53.76+5.62	<0.05
Male (n)	55	135	>0.05
Female (n)	34	81	
Insulin (n)	38	92	>0.05
Oral hypoglycemic (n)	46	129	>0.05

Table 2: frequency of oral infection according to duration.

Duration of illness	Frequency of oral fungal infection (%)
5-10yrs	56/224 (25%)
10-15yrs	22/56 (39.28%)
>15-20yrs	13/25 (52%)

DISCUSSION:

The above results show that the increasing age is the important risk factor of developing oral fungal infection in diabetic patients. However there are various studies in which this trend is not well appreciated. Relationship among the duration of diabetes and oral infection is not well established^{xi}. In the study done by lamey et al^{xii} no relationship was found between the duration of illness and oral fungal infection. However in the study mentioned above there is significant relation is showed between the duration and frequency of illness. The frequency goes on increasing with the increase in the duration of diabetes mellitus.

In this study the type of treatment plans whether the patient is on oral hypoglycemic or using insulin is not well noted^{xiii}. Similarly gender based difference have not been noted in this study. The incidence of oral candidiasis in various studies is noted more in the diabetes type 1 as compared to diabetes type 2.

Other contributory factors include the poor glycemic control of patient and poor oral hygiene. The greater HBA1C, the greater will be the frequency of oral candidiasis.

Among the fungal infections, oral candidiasis is more common in the humans. Oral candidiasis would result in the pain and discomfort or oral cavity, which would be responsible for malnutrition in the diabetes patients^{xiv}. Therefore this should be managed properly with tight glycemic control along with good oral hygiene and community awareness.

CONCLUSION:

The frequency of oral candidiasis was well associated with the duration of diabetes mellitus and age of the patient.

Gender and type of treatment i.e. oral hypoglycemic or insulin, related association was not found in this study.

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